

Figure S1. Change in score of each symptom of Modified KMI score (PP set)

* compared within groups (paired *t*-test); ** Compared between groups (two sample *t*-test).

Figure S2. Change in biochemical markers of bone turnover (PP set)

*Compared between groups (two sample *t*-test)